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ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC EXPENDITURE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study analysed the relationship between public expenditure and economic growth. The study used the secondary data from CBN Statistical Bulletin from 2004 – 2018. The objectives of this study are to examine the relationship between capital expenditure on economic services and economic growth, evaluate the relationship between capital expenditure on social and community services and economic growth, and assess the relationship between expenditure on transfers and economic growth. The Economic Growth was analysed in term of the Real Gross Domestic Product and this formed the dependent variable. The independent variable of interest was the Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services and Expenditure of Transfer. A multiple regression model was employed for the study and was analysed using the Generalized Least Square (GLS) with the aid of a statistical program (Eviews 11). The causality test was conducted using the Pairwise Granger Causality Test. The results of the hypotheses tested are that Capital Expenditure on Economic Services has a positive and significant impact on Economic Growth. Also, the study found that Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services has a negative and insignificant impact on Economic Growth and that Expenditure on Transfer has a negative and insignificant impact on Economic Growth. The study conducted a Pairwise Granger Causality Test and the result shows that causality runs from Capital Expenditure on Economic Services to Economic Growth and not from the Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services and Expenditure of Transfer. The study recommends that Capital Expenditure on Economic Services should be maintained and increased since it drives the economy positively, the productive components of the Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services should be focused on, Expenditure on Transfer (oil subsidy) should be made Zero and the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) should be encouraged.

Keywords: Public Spending, Economic Growth, Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Expenditure on Transfer.

1. Introduction

The claim on the use of fiscal policy for economic stabilization and inducement of economic growth has become of keen interest for researchers and public sector accountants. Key issue in this debate relates to the efficiency of public expenditure

in promoting economic growth. Every nation's spending draws two sides expenditure, the capital and recurrent expenditures. Public spending is a key instrument being employed by the government in controlling economic activities. The importance of public spending towards the functioning of any

economy if developed, under developed or developing cannot be ignored. The need to allocate resources efficiently among the various arms of government, as structured by their fiscal ability, capacity and responsibility gave rise to Public Finance Management. Economic growth is the increase in goods and services produced by an economy or nation, considered for a specific period of time. The rise in the country's output of goods and services is steady and constant and may be caused by an improvement in the quality of education, improvements in technology or in any way if there is a value addition in goods and services which is produced by every sector of the economy. It can be measured as a percentage increase in real gross domestic product and this means it has been adjusted for inflation. GDP is the market value of final goods & services which is produced in an economy or nation (Okoro, 2013).

The statement of the problems emanated as a result that the Nigerian Federal Government has largely spent on the recurrent expenditure and transfers over the years, and it was asserted by Oziengbe (2013) that the recurrent expenditure and expenditure on transfers are consumption spending which will not drive economic growth. The Capital expenditure known as the investment spending which drives economic growth as claimed by Kiraz and Gumus (2017) and Sedrakyan and Candamio (2017) has not been a subject of focus by the Nigerian government and this can be supported by the 2020 appropriation bill submitted by the presidency to the National Assembly on October, 2019 where the capital expenditure takes just 20.80%. Lack of public spending understanding by the majority of Nigerians and some government officials also resulted in problems for Nigeria. The Federal Government restores transfer to fuel subsidy to quell the nationwide protests which claimed more than 10 lives and witnessed 600 Nigerians injured.

Nigerians were angered on the basis that President Goodluck Jonathan's Administration removed the payment of oil subsidy which hiked the prices of petrol across the country. It was argued by the President Jonathan's Administration that removing the transfer to oil subsidy which was estimated to cost ₦2,920,000,000,000 (Two Trillion, Nine Hundred and Twenty Billion) per year would allow the government to spend money on needed public projects across Nigeria. This was also supported by Budget (2019) that the opportunity cost of transfer to subsidy are: Build and Equip 2,400 units of 1,000-bed hospitals across 774 LGAs, or 500,000 New Houses for families through mortgage at ₦20,000,000 per house.

The broad objective of this study is to analyse the impact of public expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to examine the relationship between capital expenditure on economic services and economic growth, evaluate the relationship between capital expenditure on social and community services and economic growth, and to assess the relationship between expenditure on transfers and economic growth. For the purpose of this study, the following hypotheses are stipulated in null form: There is no significant relationship between capital expenditure on economic services and economic growth. There is no significant relationship between capital expenditure on social and community services and economic growth, **and** there is no significant relationship between expenditure on transfers and economic growth.

Keynesian Hypothesis of Public Spending and Economic Growth (1936): Public expenditure is seen as a policy instrument which can be used exogenously, because it is considered to impact economic growth and correct long-term and short-term cyclical imbalances. He asserted that Public expenditure is a cause which affects economic

growth, thus the link for casualty can be seen from public expenditure to national income and not the other way round.

The Rostow-Musgrave Growth/Development Model (1969): According to their model in early stages of economic growth and development, public sector investment is seen to be high. The public sector will in turn provide the human capital in the form of spending on health, education, etc. and social capital in the form of real (bridges, roads, transport, communication system technologies, and sea port).

The Public Finance Management Theory was postulated by Erik Lindhal in 1919. This theory claims that the government should keenly and prudently control her spending to benefit the citizens. The theory however stress that the government's income should be well managed and mobilized to ward-off looting of the revenue into private accounts.

One of the studies of the relationship between public expenditures and economic growth using twenty nine (29) OECD member countries annual data from 1995-2013 was conducted by Kiraz and Gumus (2017). They used sub functions public defense-education-health expenditures to find out effect on economic growth using the Econometric Panel Methods and Granger Causality Test. They found that there is positive relationship causation between public expenditures and economic growth.

Analyzing the effect of public spending and taxes on economic growth in Spain and Armenia can be seen in the study of Sedrakyan and Candamio, (2017) the sample size was between 1996 and 2014 using the Pedroni Cointegration and Granger Causality Tests. The result was that both the recurrent and capital expenditures have a positive effect on economic growth. The study recommends increase in both recurrent and capital expenditure. This study is in consistent with the study of Bojanic (2013) but not in support of Loizides and Vamvoukas (2005)

submissions who asserted that causality is seen from the economic growth to public expenditure.

More so, in a study of public spending and economic growth in the United States, Liu et al. (2008) examined the causal relationship between the Gross Domestic Products (GDP) and public expenditure from 1947-2002 using The Granger Causality Test. The results of the causality test revealed that total spending causes growth of GDP, the Gross Domestic Products does not cause increase of public expenditure. The study reached a conclusion that since public spending grows the United States economy, as seen from the causality test. Liu et al (2008) recommend the fiscal policy authenticity and increasing in public spending. Their finding support the Keynesian hypothesis as it exerts more influence in the United States (US). This findings are also in consistent with the findings of Taiwo and Abayomi, 2011) but partly disagree with Olugbenga and Owoeye (2007).

In the study of Olugbenga and Owoeye (2007) they investigated the relationships between public spending and economic growth in a group of thirty (30) OECD countries for the period covering 1970-2005 using the OLS Regression Analysis. Their analysis showed that there is a long-run relationship between public expenditure and economic growth. The study also indicated a directional causality from public expenditure to economic growth for (sixteen) 16 countries. Their claim support the Keynesian hypothesis on this submission and Bojanic (2013). On the other hand, causality runs from economic growth to public expenditure in the remaining (fourteen) 14 countries in view, thereby disagreeing with the Keynesian hypothesis partially and agreeing with Loizides and Vamvoukas (2005) by asserting that causality can be from either the public spending to economic growth or vice-versa depending on the structure of the economy of the countries in view. They recommend that both the public expenditure and economic growth should be

expanded. The study conducted by Kiraz and Gumus (2017) agrees with this finding.

Iheanacho (2016) study investigated the short and short run relationship between public spending and economic growth in Nigeria having the period of 1986 - 2014 in view. He used the Johansen Cointegration Tool to test for stationarity of the data employed before adopting the Error Correction Method (ECM). The result of his finding revealed that recurrent spending is the major driver of the Nigeria economic growth. Controlling for the influence of other revenue order than oil, his study revealed a negative and significant long run relationship between economic growth and recurrent spending coexists with a positive short run relationship, highlighting the dual effects of recurrent spending on Nigeria economic growth. As regards the capital spending, the author's documents negative and significant long run effect of capital spending on economic growth in Nigeria. Decomposition of the variance confirms the collective contribution of government expenditure on economic growth. He however recommends that public funds should be released on impactful projects rather than spending it on projects that will not grow the economy positively. His findings are in consistent with the submission of Oziengbe (2013), Bleaney, Gemmell and Kneller (2001) and Sedrakyan and Candamio (2017).

Available literatures have shown that studies have been conducted on the impacts of public expenditure on economic growth. However, the findings of these studies have produced mixed and inconclusive results and expenditure of transfer has not been a major focus.

2. Materials And Methods

Ex post facto was employed for this study and the population is 15years observations (2004-2018). The independent variables are Capital Expenditure on Economic Services and Capital Expenditure on

Social and Community Services and Expenditure on Transfers while the dependent variable is the Real Gross Domestic Products (RGDP). The Pairwise Granger Causality Test was conducted to see the causality link between public expenditure and economic growth. This study then employed the Generalized Least Square (GLS) method to obtain the prediction coefficients of the Eviews 11. The model Specification is as follow: Economic Growth =f(Public Expenditure), GDP = f(Cecos, Csocs, Extrf), $GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 cecos_t + \beta_2 csocs_t + \beta_3 extrf_t + \epsilon_t$. Where: *GDP* = Gross Domestic Product (proxy for economic growth), α_0 = Coefficient of the constant variable, β_1, β_2 = Regression of the coefficient of the independent variable, Cecos = Capital Expenditure on Economic Services, Csocs = Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services, Extrf = Expenditure on Transfers, ϵ = the error term, which is also known as Epsilon, t = at time t (annual time series), The apriori expectations of the variables are given as ($\beta_1 > 0; \beta_2 > 0 \beta_3 < 0$) i.e. $cecos > 0, csocs > 0$ and $extrf < 0$.

3. Results Table 1: Growth data for rgdp, cecos, csocs and extrf from 2004 – 2018

Year	Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) (? ' Billion)	Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (? ' Billion)	Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (? ' Billion)	Expenditure on Transfers (? ' Billion)
2004	331	78.74	-25.71	42.20
2005	245	97.78	41.33	36.7
2006	252	-2.82	7.32	16.51
2007	292	96.17	72.22	6.89
2008	309	145.91	1.27	60.27
2009	384	2	7.24	9.65
2010	475	-93.81	6.84	29.1
2011	289	-25.8	-58.92	277.68
2012	241	-65.5	4.55	-73.6
2013	328	184.87	57.31	-17.53
2014	393	44.7	-43.42	-10.5
2015	187	-44.7	-28.31	-38.82
2016	-109	-69.8	-14.18	706.29
2017	599	263.24	98.86	-610.43
2018	130	211.3	35.76	22.05

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2019

Table 2. Generalized Least Squares

Dependent Variable: GDP
 Method: Generalized Least Squares
 Date: 11/17/19 Time: 01:42
 Sample: 1 15 (2004 2018)
 Included observations: 15

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	29938040	5885820.	5.086469	0.0004
CECOS	41314.48	36169.51	1.142246	0.0487
CSOCS	-16811.24	109607.9	-0.153376	0.8809
EXTRF	-33759.03	8211.460	-4.111209	0.2776
R-squared	0.738309	Mean dependent var		55263521
Adjusted R-squared	0.666939	S.D. dependent var		12519788
S.E. of regression	7225353.	Akaike info criterion		34.64727
Sum squared resid	5.74E+14	Schwarz criterion		34.83608
Log likelihood	-255.8545	Hannan-Quinn criter.		34.64526
F-statistic	10.34477	Durbin-Watson stat		1.737793
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001563			

Source: E-Views 11 result, 2019

In the regression analysis table 2, the Coefficient of CECOS is in line with the apriori expectations (CECOS > 0). CECOS has a positive coefficient of 41314.48 significant at 5% level which means that a percentage change (increase) in capital expenditure on economic services will increase the RGDP by 41314.48% positive unit change. The P-value is 0.0487 and since the P-value (0.0487) < 0.05 (5% level of significance), this study reject the null hypothesis 1 (H₀) and conclude that the level of capital expenditure on economic services has significant on economic growth in Nigeria.

CSOCS did not confirm this study's apriori expectation of (CSOCS > 0) it has a negative coefficient of -16811.24, and not significant which means that a percentage change (increase) in capital expenditure on social and community services will induce a -16811.24% (as approximated) negative unit change in RGDP. The P-value is 0.8809, and since the P-value (0.8809) > 0.05 (5% level of significance), this study accept the null hypothesis 2 (H₀) and conclude that capital expenditure on social and economic services does not have a significant relationship on economic growth in Nigeria.

Also, EXTRF confirmed the apriori expectation of this study, this study expected EXTRF to have a negative impact on the RGDP since it is seen as consumption spending of which subsidy payment is inclusive and as seen on table 2, the coefficient is negative (-33759.03) and not significant which implies that when EXTRF increases by 1 unit, the RGDP also decreases by 33759.03. The P-value is 0.2776, and since the P-value (0.2776) > 0.05 (5% level of significance), this study accept the null hypothesis 3 (H₀) and conclude that expenditure on transfer does not have a significant relationship on economic growth in Nigeria.

The coefficient of determination as revealed by R-square (R²) indicates that 74% of the variations observed in the dependent variable (RGDP) were explained by combined influence and variations in the explanatory variables (CECOS, CSOCS and EXTRF) and the other 26% is attributed to other factors not included in the model. The F-statistics which test the goodness of fit confirms that the model employed in the study is statistically significant given the value as 10.34477, and equation is useful in explaining a unit change in Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. On the whole, the overall probability (F-statistics) is 0.001563 significant at 5% i.e. (0.001563 < 0.05). The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistics is equal to 1.7; thus implying the absence of serial auto-correlation. This is because when the DW value is closer to two, it is an evidence of the absence of serial correlation.

From table 4, the result of the pairwise Granger Causality Test shows that only Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (CECOS) has significant causal impact on the Gross Domestic Product in the period under review while the other explanatory variables capital expenditure on social and community services (CSOCS) and expenditure on transfer (EXTRF) are not significant in the GDP growth.

4. Discussion:

Table 3: Summary of the regression result

Variables	CECOS	CSOCS	EXTRF	R ²	Adj. R ²	F- Stat
Model – RGDP (Sig)	41314.48 (0.0487)	-16811.24 (0.8809)	-33759.03 (0.2776)	0.738309	0.666939	10.344 77
Akaike Info criterion: 34.64727	Schwarz Info criterion: 34.83608	Hannan-Quinn criter.: 34.64526	Probability 0.001563	-	-	-

Source: Derived from regression result, 2019; Significance Level is at **5%

Based on the summary of the regression in table 3, the results indicate that Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (CECOS) is positively related and have significant impact on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). The result is consistent with the findings of Sedrakyan and Candamio (2017), and Oziengbe (2013) but disagreed with Akpan (2005) who found an insignificant impact and a negative relationship between the Real Gross Domestic Product and Capital Expenditure on Economic Services. Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (CSOCS) and Expenditure on Transfer (EXTRF) are negatively related and have

insignificant impact on Real Gross Domestic Product. This claim supports previous studies as seen in Akpan (2005) and Iheanacho (2016) as their study found a positive and significant relationship between RGDP and CECOS. CECOS was statistically significant, while CSOCS and EXTRF are statistically insignificant in explaining the variation in Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. From the result the a-priori expectation Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (CECOS) greater than 0 proved to be true being positively signed, Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (CSOCS) apriori expectation is $CSOCS > 0$ but the result of the regression showed a negatively signed response as $CSOCS < 0$ and statistically insignificant in explaining the variation in Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria, while Expenditure on Transfer proved to be negatively related to RGDP being negatively signed and it is statistically insignificant in explaining the variation in Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria.

The estimation results reveal that the explanatory variables jointly account for approximately 74% percentage changes in economic growth. The Durbin Watson statistic (1.7) illustrates the absence of auto correlation. A 1% percentage increase in Capital Expenditure on Economic Services causes economic growth to increase by 4131448%. Similarly, a 1% increase in Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services leads to 1681124% decrease in economic growth. Furthermore, a 1% increases on Expenditure on Transfers results to a decrease in economic growth by approximately 33759.03%. Thus, higher government spending on capital expenditure on economic services enable environment for businesses to strive through reduced cost of production and access to social facilities. Besides, the estimation shows that a 1% increase in government expenditure on social and community services causes economic growth to decline by approximately 16811.24%. This is not surprising because funds meant for the development of the social and community services sector have not been properly utilized and in most cases embezzled, thus precipitating the incessant traveling out by citizens, politicians and high government official seeking for medical solution or academic pursuit. Moreover, the estimation result indicates that a 1%

increase in expenditure on transfer leads to approximately 33759.03% decrease in economic growth.

5. Conclusion

Based on the regression results in table 2 and 3, this work has so far explained the theories of government expenditure by relevant scholars such as the Keynesian Hypothesis of Public Spending (1936), the Rostow-Musgrave Growth/Development Model (1969) and the Public Finance Management Theory (1919). According to Keynes, he asserted that Public expenditure is a cause which affect economic growth, thus the link for casualty can be seen from public expenditure to economic growth and not the other way round. Public Finance Management Theory claims that the government should keenly and prudently control her spending to benefit the citizens. The theory however stress that the government's income should be well managed and mobilized to ward-off looting of the revenue into private accounts.

Looking at the three (3) theories listed above, this informs us that different current situation and government activities and functions have made some of the theories invalid as concentration by the scholars were made as regards the economic situation as of that time as seen that war was frequent during that time, transfers on oil subsidy was not inclusive and recurrent expenditure which is a consumption spending was not duly explain in relation to capital spending.

The secondary data gathered were regressed and it shows clearly that there is a positive relationship and significant impact between RGDP and capital expenditure on economic services and expenditure on transfer while capital expenditure on social and community services has a negative relationship and an insignificant impact between RGDP. This result supports the Keynesian Hypothesis of Public Spending who showed a positive relationship between CECOS, CSOCS and EXTRF respectively on RGDP since he asserted that causality runs from public expenditure to economic growth and not the other way round. However, the Keynesian hypothesis did not consider the Public Finance Management Theory by Erik Lindhal (1919) and expenditure on transfer.

A fact has been established that there is an impact of government spending in relation to the economic growth of Nigeria and vice versa. It can

therefore be said that the higher the government spends in productive sectors of the capital investments, the higher the level of economic growth (*ceteris paribus*) and the lower the government spending, the lower the level of economic growth of the nation but it should be noted that not all government spending bring about economic growth therefore, government needs to understand the sector that drives growth before increasing spending in such sector. In general, the empirical evidence suggests that the increase in the government spending should be based on the fact that the Public Finance Management Theory is in view.

The study further concludes that the components of government expenditure considered in this study are important variables in explaining economic growth in Nigeria. In the Nigeria experience as shown by the results; Nigeria partly confirms the Keynesian hypothesis and a new theory to cover the gaps of the Keynesian hypothesis was formulated.

5.1. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study in the regression analysis table 2 and 3, the following recommendations are presented:

- i. Capital expenditure on economic services should be increased since it was found to impact the real gross domestic product positively and since refinery is under the capital expenditure on economic services, it is highly recommended for the government to expand the production so as to null off the negative effect of transfers (subsidy payment on oil import and price equalization). There should be a consistent plan as regards the Public Private Partnership (PPP) in reducing the recurrent spending while expanding the expenditure on economic services.
- ii. Since capital expenditure on social and community services will impact the economic growth negatively if not expanded; this means that productive social and community activities should be increased. This will stimulate activities in the social and community services sector and, perhaps, reverse its negative effect on economic growth. There is need for government to pay more attention to the Public Finance Management Theory. This brings accountability, prudence, fairness, and good governance the budgetary, allocation and spending of public funds in the capital expenditure on social

and community services.

- iii. The analysis showed that expenditure on transfer have a negative effect on economic growth, therefore, expenditure on transfers should be made 0 especially on the non performing functions.

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7. TABLES:

Table 1: Growth data for rgdp, cecos, csocs and extrf from 2004 – 2018

Year	Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) (? ' Billion)	Capital Expenditure on Economic Services (? ' Billion)	Capital Expenditure on Social and Community Services (? ' Billion)	Expenditure on Transfers (? ' Billion)
2004	3311101.69	78.74	-25.71	42.20
2005	2454400.08	97.78	41.33	36.7
2006	2520555.39	-2.82	7.32	16.51
2007	2926903.38	96.17	72.22	6.89
2008	3090107.38	145.91	1.27	60.27
2009	3843583.77	2	7.24	9.65
2010	4756165.10	-93.81	6.84	29.1
2011	2898777.59	-25.8	-58.92	277.68
2012	2418851.27	-65.5	4.55	-73.6
2013	3288828.69	184.87	57.31	-17.53
2014	3934064.11	44.7	-43.42	-10.5
2015	1871144.10	-44.7	-28.31	-38.82
2016	-1092694.01	-69.8	-14.18	706.29
2017	559744.41	263.24	98.86	-610.43
2018	1308961.61	211.3	35.76	22.05

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2019

Table 2. Generalized Least Squares
 Dependent Variable: GDP
 Method: Generalized Least Squares
 Date: 11/17/19 Time: 01:42
 Sample: 1 15 (2004 2018)
 Included observations: 15

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	29938040	5885820.	5.086469	0.0004
CECOS	41314.48	36169.51	1.142246	0.0487
CSOCS	-16811.24	109607.9	-0.153376	0.8809
EXTRF	-33759.03	8211.460	-4.111209	0.2776
R-squared	0.738309	Mean dependent var		55263521
Adjusted R-squared	0.666939	S.D. dependent var		12519788
S.E. of regression	7225353.	Akaike info criterion		34.64727
Sum squared resid	5.74E+14	Schwarz criterion		34.83608
Log likelihood	-255.8545	Hannan-Quinn criter.		34.64526
F-statistic	10.34477	Durbin-Watson stat		1.737793
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001563			

Source: E-Views II result, 2019

Table 3: Summary of the regression result

Variables	CECOS	CSOCS	EXTRF	R ²	Adj. R ²	F-Stat
Model – RGDP (Sig)	41314.48 (0.0487)	-16811.24 (0.8809)	-33759.03 (0.2776)	0.738309	0.666939	10.34477
Akaike Info criterion: 34.64727	Schwarz Info criterion: 34.83608	Hannan-Quinn criter.: 34.64526	Probability 0.001563	-	-	-

Source: Derived from regression result, 2019; Significance Level is at **5%

Table 4: Pairwise granger causality test
 Pairwise Granger Causality Tests
 Date: 11/23/19 Time: 08:06
 Sample: 1 15 (2004 2018)
 Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
CECOS does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause CECOS	14	7.82283 2.12385	0.0174 2.9946
CSOCS does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause CSOCS	14	0.19062 1.57843	0.6708 0.2350
EXTRF does not Granger Cause RGDP RGDP does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	0.13012 0.31290	0.7251 0.5871
CSOCS does not Granger Cause CECOS CECOS does not Granger Cause CSOCS	14	0.06244 0.10493	0.8073 0.7521
EXTRF does not Granger Cause CECOS CECOS does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	15.5109 7.06660	0.0023 0.0223
EXTRF does not Granger Cause CSOCS CSOCS does not Granger Cause EXTRF	14	1.99159 0.12141	0.1858 0.7341

Source: Eviews 11 Result, 2019

Contribution to Knowledge

In line with the results and to fill the identified gaps, this study added expenditure on transfer to the model. This study claim that cause and effect runs from public spending to economic growth as seen in the Pairwise Granger Causality Test, this study agree partially with the Keynesian's theory of public finance and economic growth. The disagreement is as a result that the Keynesian theory (1936) did not capture expenditure on transfer as the model only fit into the economic situation of that time hence the theory has been weakened by "time" and "occurrences". In the light of this, this study developed a public finance and economic growth/development theory that fill all the gaps listed above. The theory is called "Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth/Development of 2019"

Explaining table 5, public spending comprises of the recurrent expenditure, capital expenditure and expenditure on transfer. The recurrent expenditure and expenditure on transfer won't drive economic growth since they are consumption expenditures. They won't drive economic growth; the capital expenditure is an investment spending which this study believes drives economic growth. In light of this, this study claim that recurrent expenditure should be kept minimal since it can't be equal to zero, as an increase in the capital expenditure will definitely expand the recurrent expenditure, though not in the same proportion. Some capital expenditure should be increased in particular, the performing functions while some functions decreased and this should be observed in respect to the public finance management theory by Erik Lindhal in 1919 and expenditure on transfer should be made to zero especially, the non performing functions since it has a negative impact on the economic growth. To reduce the recurrent expenditure and increase the capital spending, the Public Private Partnership (PPP) should be encouraged.

Table 5: Olonite Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth / Development (2019)

Version	Functions and Notations	Valid when
Olonite	Gross Domestic Product = f(Public Spending)	β > 0
Theory of Public Finance and Economic Growth/Development (2019)	Gross Domestic Product = f(Recurrent Expenditure, Capital Expenditure, Transfer)	
	$GDP_t = \alpha + \beta * PS_t^{\Theta, \downarrow, \uparrow, 0} + \square_t$	
	$GDP_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta * (REEXP, CAEXP, EXTRF)_t^{\Theta, \downarrow, \uparrow, 0} + \square_t$	
	$GDP_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta * (REEXP^{\downarrow}, CAEXP^{\Theta(\downarrow \text{a-or-d-} \downarrow)}, EXTRF^{\Theta(\downarrow \text{a-or-d-} \downarrow)})_t + \square_t$	
	$GDP_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta * (REEXP^{\downarrow}, CAEXP^{\Theta(\downarrow \text{a-or-d-} \downarrow)}, EXTRF^{\Theta(\downarrow \text{a-or-d-} \downarrow)})_t + \square_t$	

Source: Author's Computation and Design 2019;

Notes: "→ ↑" means: "to increase", "↓" means: "reduce", "↕" means: "increase and reduce", "0" means: "make zero". "Θ" means: "some", PS denotes Public Spending, GDP means Gross Domestic Product, "↓" means non-performing, "a-or-d" means aggregated or disaggregated functions.